

ATTITUDES TO PSYCHOLOGICAL MANIPULATION IN SOCIETY AND ITS PLACE IN HUMAN LIFE

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Abstract. *This article shows that the technologies of manipulation are multiplying in number by today, they are becoming more universally influential on the human mind, their ability to penetrate the human psyche and convincingly influence the public and individual consciousness of citizens, their value attitude and political worldview the increasing power is highlighted. At the same time, along with the diversity of existing technologies, special attention was paid to the fact that the theoretical foundations of the issue are still very weak: uniform approaches to its study by various humanitarian sciences have not been formed, no explanatory model of manipulative influence has been developed, no classification of manipulation techniques and technologies has been given.*

Keywords: *manipulation technologies, manipulation techniques, manipulation, consciousness, power of influence, method, manipulator, personality, communication, information, people management, hidden influence.*

Being active in all aspects in our social life today, having one's own goals and plans, thinking in accordance with the needs of the times, being able to objectively assess and analyze any changes occurring in social life are among the characteristics of today's people. Based on their worldview, today's people are not only aware of the news of our rapidly developing society, but also of the events happening in the whole world that has a great impact on news with his curiosity and creativity. In our fast-paced life, there are many opinions about the presence of alien forces that are trying to manipulate and influence our worldview, thoughts, and our relationships with the realities of the social environment in hidden ways. In fact, it is possible to change or control the mind of a person by influencing his psychology through various manipulative tactics. In order to clarify such points, it is necessary to clarify the concept of manipulation first.

Manipulations have been used in political practice for centuries, but in the last two centuries they have increasingly taken the form of a coherent professional set of methods, styles and forms of manipulative influence, i.e. "technologies of manipulation".

In recent years, the number of manipulative technologies has increased many times, they have become more universal, the power of persuasive influence on the public and individual consciousness of citizens, their value attitude and political outlook has increased. Along with the diversity of existing technologies, the theoretical foundations of the issue are still very weak: uniform approaches to its study by various humanitarian sciences have not been formed, an explanatory model of manipulative influence has not been developed, and a complete classification of manipulation techniques and technologies has not been given.

It is not enough to describe the theoretical foundations of this phenomenon, to consider the existing manipulation technologies and to describe their role in the modern political process in order to compose its elements. need This task is complicated by the fact that there is still no unity in the definition of the term "manipulation" among scientists: today manipulation is called various effects, the number and direction of which is constantly increasing. This fact, together with the

interdisciplinary nature of this phenomenon, makes it difficult to search for a single methodological framework that can integrate and organize knowledge about it within a unified approach. Thus, in the dictionaries of European languages, the word "manipulation" refers to the control of objects with certain intentions, while the presence of dexterity in performing manipulation actions (manual control, manual examination of a patient by a doctor) is emphasized [1. 47 p]. Different researchers emphasize different signs necessary to identify this phenomenon. Thus, according to R. Godin, "manipulation is the power used secretly and against the will of another person" [2. 18 p]. B. N. Bessonov believes that manipulation is a form of spiritual influence carried out by force, a form of hidden domination [3. 123-p]. L. Proto understands manipulation as a "hidden effect on selection" [4. 53-p]. W. Ricker understands this phenomenon as "such a structure of the world that allows victory" [5. 114-p]. E. Shostrom offers a similar definition, in which manipulation is understood as "management and control, exploitation of another, use as objects, things or things" [6. 70-p].

E.L. Dotsenko tried to give the most general definition of this phenomenon based on the analysis of the signs shown by these authors [7. 344-p]. He conducted a synthesis of these concepts, the most commonly accepted criteria of manipulation among researchers are: "stealth, abstraction", "exploitation, domination", "management, control", "using another person as an object", "indirect influence". transfer" and "programming thoughts, intentions ". E.L. In addition to the above points, Dotsenko points to less common signs of manipulation: "playing on weak points", "violence", "desire for one-sided profit" [7. 40-p].

As a result of the work done, E.L. Dotsenko proposes to understand manipulation as "a type of psychological influence, the skillful implementation of which leads to the hidden excitement of another person's intentions that do not correspond to his true desires" [7. 22-p].

It should also be emphasized that manipulation in this case is not equated with lying. Because a lie means the opposite of the truth. Manipulation is not the opposite of reality, but an attempt to change reality in order to achieve one's goals using various methods of influence. This was well described by J. Rudinov: "Someone asks us for directions to Minsk, and we falsely direct them to Pinsk - this is just cheating. In the second case, if we deceive a person who wants to go to Minsk because we want to go to Pinsk, then manipulation takes place. Thus, J. Rudinov considers manipulation as the object's hidden motivation for the action necessary for the manipulator.

Explaining the nature of political manipulation, G.V. Pushkareva cites the example of J. Rudinova in the political sphere: "Manipulation occurs when a voter actually wants to vote for candidate N, but changes his choice under external influence and votes for candidate M." Or the voter doesn't really want to go to the polls at all, but at the last moment changes his mind and comes to the polling station to participate in the election. Or else a person might not want to participate in a protest at all, but he might unexpectedly find himself among the protestors. Or he did not want to get involved in the political debate, but he is cleverly provoked by external forces to express his views in this political debate."

Taking into account the opinions of the above scientists, we conducted a small online survey. Below we will introduce you to the results of this survey.

Diagramm 1

44 respondents took part in our online survey. Representatives of different ages took part in this survey, and here we consider it permissible to say that most of them are students studying in higher education. As you can see in Chart 1, "How do you feel about people who lie?" to our question, 72.7% of the participants have a negative attitude, 20.5% have an indifferent attitude, and 6.8% of our participants have a positive attitude towards lies. It can be seen from this that people have become victims of lies many times in their lives and this feeling proves that it is possible to have an aggressive attitude towards the person who used lies.

Diagramm 2

18.2% of our respondents chose the answer to the question, "What would you do if you noticed that your loved ones lied to you?" 36.4% of the participants answered that I cannot predict what I will do, and 45.5% answered that I would tell myself that our participant is lying. Based on the results, we can say that in diagram 1, "How do you feel about people who lie?" to our question, 72.7% of the participants said that they have a negative opinion, but now the participants who know that the person telling the lie is their relative are hesitating, that is, only 45.5% of the participants said that they are firm in their opinion. It follows that the proximity of a person who is lying to us indicates a high probability of falling under his influence.

Diagramm 3

As you can see in the diagram 3, 70.5% of the participants answered "If you are appointed as a leader in an organization, do you think that you will be able to manage the employees under you?" They answered that they can definitely manage it. 22.7% of our respondents stated that they could not say anything in advance, while the remaining 6.8% of our participants stated that they do not have leadership skills. We tried to find the difference between the respondents who answered "of course I can manage" and the respondents who answered "I can't say anything in advance" and we came across the age difference that separates them. We observed that most of our participants who believe in their own strength and say that they can manage, are 18-22-year-old students. We observed that most of our participants who answered "I can't say anything in advance" and "I don't think I have leadership skills" were younger than those who answered "I can definitely manage." Based on this, we can say that the feeling of being able to control others can be strong among young people. At the same time, life experience and the ability to correctly assess one's own capabilities will be formed as the youth passes.

Diagramm 4

In diagram 4 above, "Imagine you stopped the car on your way home and realized that you had no money. What would you do in that situation?" to our question, 40.9% of our respondents chose the answer that they would explain the situation and ask them to take them home. 31.8% of

the participants chose to excuse themselves from the allocation and walk home. The remaining 27.3% of the participants said that they did not have money for the fare and left it to the discretion of the taxi driver. As can be seen from this diagram, we can see that 40.9% of the research participants strongly try to manipulate the allocation, while 27.3% of the respondents want to try to manipulate the allocation at a slightly slower level. Only 31.8% of the participants did not want to have a psychological impact on the allocation. It follows that 68.2% of the participants use manipulation and want to take the allocation under their influence in order to satisfy their needs.

Diagramm 5

In diagram 5, we answer the question that clearly shows the manipulation of people, that is, "You don't have enough money in the market for something you have wanted for a long time. How would you proceed?" to our question, 77.3% of our respondents chose the answer "I would try to lower the price, if I could lower it or not", 22.7% of the respondents chose the answer "I would argue until the price reaches the level that I can afford." The most interesting thing is that none of our respondents chose the answer option "I surrendered to fate and returned home". Based on this, we can say that the majority of people do not tolerate psychological influence on another person in the way of their goal, and the remaining large number of people try to achieve this goal, i.e. try to influence them. But they don't give up without trying.

Based on the above data and research results, we can conclude that every person can be a manipulator. And it should be noted that manipulation is not always negative. Because in life, a person does not always focus on someone else for his own benefit, but he can also use lies for his benefit, and exert psychological influence on him for his benefit. For example, a doctor may comfort the patient by saying, "You are in very good health, but you are a little tired" while hiding the patient's true condition. Otherwise, if the patient finds out about the true state of his health, his health may worsen. But in our society today, many people put their own interests first. Because of this, there are more negative attitudes towards manipulation in society. For our opinion, I can say that whether a person wants it or not, a manipulator can also be a person under the influence of manipulation.

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